

Month	long	lat	C:Chl a	R/V
Jan	39.03	43.5	21	36-PV
Jan	37.56	43.5	55	36-PV
Jan	38	43.5	68	36-PV
Feb	34.2	43.4	40	36-PV
Feb	32.3	43.4	56	36-PV
Feb	41.03	41.9	15	21-Vityaz
Feb	39.36	42.34	38	21-Vityaz
Feb	37.68	43.17	59	21-Vityaz
Feb	35.77	44.02	62	21-Vityaz
Feb	34.14	44.07	64	21-Vityaz
Feb	35.6	44.02	21	21-Vityaz
Feb	33.88	43.26	62	21-Vityaz
Mar	35.9	44	79	15-Vityaz
Mar	32.56	43.36	72	15-Vityaz
Mar	31.34	43.9	51	15-Vityaz
Mar	35.92	43.9	47	15-Vityaz
Mar	32.64	43.54	39	15-Vityaz
Apr	31.33	44.17	160	41-PV
Apr	31.85	43.85	124	41-PV
Apr	32.34	43.51	51	41-PV
Apr	32.85	44.50	47	41-PV
Apr	33.34	43.50	158	41-PV
Apr	31.83	44.17	79	41-PV
Apr	32.34	43.83	50	41-PV
Apr	32.83	43.5	52	41-PV
May	32.1	43.12	122	72-PV
May	32.1	43.14	101	72-PV
May	32.1	43.14	108	72-PV
May	31.95	44.1	121	72-PV
May	31.85	44.2	124	72-PV
Jun	31.26	41.5	189	Bilim
Jun	31.26	41.68	120	Bilim
Jun	33.26	42.26	190	Bilim
Jun	30.77	42.85	113	Bilim
Jun	31.77	42.85	275	Bilim
Jun	32.26	43.17	120	Bilim
Jun	32.26	44.5	149	33-PV
Jun	35.26	44.5	114	33-PV
Jun	33.26	44	175	33-PV
Jun	36.26	44	190	33-PV
Jun	34.26	43.5	175	33-PV
Jun	37.26	43.5	148	33-PV
Jun	32.26	43.17	167	33-PV
Jun	38.26	43	158	33-PV
Jun	39.26	42.5	179	33-PV
Jun	41	42	151	33-PV
Jun	32.26	42.85	251	Bilim
Jun	33.26	42.85	255	Bilim
Jun	31.26	43.17	105	Bilim
Jul	32.17	44.48	210	37-PV
Jul	37.26	44.46	155	37-PV
Jul	37.29	44.00	161	37-PV
Jul	38.29	43.50	165	37-PV
Jul	38.26	41.85	174	Bilim

Jul	40.26	41.26	172	Bilim
Jul	39.26	41.26	166	Bilim
Jul	37.77	42.85	183	Bilim
Aug	34.5	44.08	164	70-PV
Aug	32.17	43.35	140	70-PV
Aug	32.17	43.35	205	70-PV
Aug	32.17	43.35	132	70-PV
Aug	32	44	235	70-PV
Sep	32.48	43.23	120	Parshin
Sep	32.5	43.65	266	Parshin
Sep	31.6	44.23	155	Parshin
Sep	30.55	43.62	194	Parshin
Sep	30.13	43.69	240	Parshin
Oct	31.60	44.25	107	67-PV
Oct	32.48	44.58	134	67-PV
Oct	32.08	44.30	72	67-PV
Nov	31.97	43.9	50	35-PV
Nov	36.17	44	109	35-PV
Nov	32.26	44.32	70	35-PV
Dec	31.25	44.17	25	32-PK
Dec	31.75	44.33	55	32-PK
Dec	31.75	43.84	70	32-PK
Dec	32.25	43.5	23	32-PK
Dec	32.75	43.5	42	32-PK